

CYBER SECURITY RISKS OF IoT DEVICES

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Annotation. *The article presents possible cybersecurity risks of IoT devices. The information security of consumer IoT devices is shown. They offer a set of security services such as protection against DDoS attacks, protection of WEB applications, etc. The concepts of who “Cybercriminals” are are given.*

Keywords: *IoT security, IoT products, IoT devices, IoT email authentication, cybersecurity risks, cybercriminals, Dataplan system.*

INTRODUCTION

IoT or “Internet of Things” is the entire collection of devices that can be connected to a network. It is growing at a tremendous pace, both quantitatively and qualitatively: new devices for a wide variety of purposes are appearing, from household appliances to vehicles, from production machines to reading devices. Despite all the prospects that the integration of IoT devices into everyday life and business processes opens up, there are also a lot of risks. And if socio-economic ones threaten only in the future, then cybersecurity risks are relevant now. In this article we will discuss the reasons for the vulnerability of IoT devices, the risks associated with them and possible consequences.

Machine learning technologies open up new prospects for the development of the Internet of Things, but they also bring with them new threats: the creation of individual malware samples, the generation of fake events, the emergence of digital doubles of real law-abiding users, etc. The Internet of Things has become a tasty prey for hackers and a source of new threats. In such conditions, how can we minimize the risks of losing the reliability of Internet of Things systems and what security standards should we use? The situation is aggravated by numerous factors: the emergence of different standards and interfaces caused by the diversity of devices; complexity of managing geographically distributed sensors, etc.; the presence of different protocols, data formats and changing addresses of target sources; the need to ensure the required performance when scaling storage; the need for continuous monitoring of the network topology and maintaining its performance [1].

DISTRIBUTION OF IoT DEVICES

The Internet of Things has become firmly entrenched in both business and everyday life. This was facilitated by several factors: Industrial development. Back in 2011, German industrialists coined the term “Industry 4.0” (in some sources – “Economy 4.0”), which denotes the transition to automated production and total digitalization of industry. The concept involves reducing human functions at a conventional plant to operator and administrative functions. Reducing the cost of production and operation of IoT devices. Development of local network infrastructure, reduction in the cost of digital elements in devices. Comfort and optimization. Technological devices, with a sufficient level of “user literacy,” are simply more convenient and functional. This also includes a new user experience that also attracts the consumer.

We cannot ignore such a factor as marketing. After all, the IoT concept allows you to “sell” the same coffee machine, printer or vacuum cleaner to the client again (due to additional functions)

and at a higher price. The growth in the number of IoT devices is directly related to the increase in Internet channel capacity, which means that security tools will need to withstand significant loads, analyzing and processing gigantic traffic flows in order to identify what devices are “communicating” about. Just imagine that all the cars in the city suddenly became “smart” and began to interact with each other and build routes. All this traffic will have to be analyzed to ensure its legitimacy in order to avoid consequences. The main trend in the context of IoT security is an increase in the performance of security tools: increasing speed and deepening the analysis of the device interaction protocol.

Regarding the use of IoT devices in production, opinions are quite mixed. On the one hand, this allows you to significantly optimize the process itself and reduce the number of required personnel. On the other hand, such production becomes acutely dependent on the supplier company or other contractors who will provide service for such equipment, its setup and adequate functioning within the network [2].

CYBERSECURITY RISKS IN THE CONTEXT OF IoT

The problem of Internet of Things security is quite acute, and was first raised in the early 2000s. **Lack of uniform standards.** Regulating this process will help improve the protection of IoT devices from cyber attacks. First of all, it is necessary to create recommendations, detailed instructions on how to ensure the protection of the Internet of things from outside interference.

For example, this year Xiaomi announced its proposal for cybersecurity standards for such devices. It lists the standards, OS for them, communications and integration between IoT devices, as well as requirements for privacy and data protection in this segment. The corporation proposes to scale its offerings to unified global IoT standards that other companies can use. It is also necessary to introduce responsibility for developers and manufacturers of IoT devices for their security and the safety of user data [3].

In world practice, there are no requirements or regulations that would oblige the manufacturer to in any way ensure the safety of their products. This is possible for two reasons: Security is not a priority for the user. Many people simply do not know about information security risks at the everyday level. Commercial feasibility does not always imply the creation of safe products. Developing secure devices and guaranteeing their resistance to malicious influence is simply unnecessary (and rather harmful) in the context of making a profit. Not all manufacturers are willing to bear such costs. As a result, there are a huge number of devices on the market (about 7 billion by the end of 2022, according to Gartner), a significant percentage of which have zero security [4].

CYBERCRIMINALS

Hacker activity in the context of IoT devices has been at a low level for a long time. Most often, they were used as “auxiliary devices” when masking traffic within the company’s infrastructure. Over time, the situation has changed, as IoT devices turned out to be: poorly protected or not protected at all; suitable for botnetting and mining. The third aspect is that this type of device has become much more common, including in the business environment, in enterprises and production. This made it an independent target for APT attacks.

Risks from the information security point of view of consumer IoT devices have always been relevant. For example, smart household appliances are often hacked to create botnet networks, which are actively used by hackers to attack the infrastructure of organizations. To protect the infrastructure of companies, a set of security services is offered, such as protection against DDoS attacks, protection of WEB applications, etc. Devices for IoT products are connected directly through the operator’s network infrastructure in accordance with the international

standards of the 3GPP consortium. Also, connected devices immediately fall into a dedicated APN within the network. In this way, devices connect to the IoT platform without accessing the open Internet. And since the devices are not present on the Internet, attackers will not be able to connect to them to hack. Despite the fact that hackers still prefer PCs and smartphones as targets for hacking, the number of attacks on IoT devices is sure to grow in proportion to the increase in their number in various types of organizations [5].

Popular IoT platforms - Google Cloud IoT and AWS IoT - allow you to apply machine-learning models along with appropriate configuration tools when working with devices. AWS IoT Greengrass ML Inference enables inference directly on devices using models trained and optimized in the cloud. The cloud-based machine-learning platform Amazon SageMaker provides tools for creating a predictive model for analyzing video recordings - cameras can independently detect suspicious activity and send notifications. For example, if illegitimate activity is detected near a bank terminal, the smart camera itself will determine that the attacker is planning a hack and call the police. Conversely, data captured by IoT Greengrass can be sent back to SageMaker, where it is enriched and used to improve the quality of machine learning models. The Dataplan system from Angara Technologies Group works in a similar scenario, allowing it to process data from target sources in the Internet of Things and train a neural network model to identify anomalies and deviations in the behavior of equipment.

CONCLUSIONS

According to Gartner's 2023 forecast for the security maturity cycle of IoT devices, the next round of business interest should be expected within two to five years. There is already a noticeable paradigm shift regarding the attitude towards the Internet of Things: security is perceived less and less as a side characteristic, and more often as a mandatory property of a device. At the same time, there are already quite reliable ways to protect a group of devices included in a company's network. In the near future, for companies that use technological devices and devices, the services of organizations that can not only integrate such a device into the infrastructure but also ensure its security through the creation of several echelons of defense will be especially relevant. Modern solutions that allow complex application tasks to be performed, but do not have proper protection, jeopardize the performance and safety of the entire system. The use of systems to support distributed mathematical calculations, large-scale data warehouses, and complexes based on continuously learning neural networks that do not have a clearly defined role model provides an advantage, but at the same time leads to an increase in threats to information security.

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